

AUTHOR MARKS IN EXTREMIST TEXT

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Annotation: In accordance with the new version of the law "On countering extremist activity", a criminal offense is not only the publication (replication, popularization) of extremist works, but also the creation of texts of extremist content. If earlier investigative practice encountered only the figure of the Distributor, then from now on, a completely new figure, the Author, should enter the field of professional vision of operatives. Apparently, this innovation will cause certain difficulties in investigative and judicial practice: distribution is a concrete, physical act, while the creation of a text is a creative process that is not fixed by the usual methods of forensic science.

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In accordance with the new version of the Law "On Counteracting Extremist Activity"¹, a criminal offense is not only the publication (replication, popularization) of extremist works, but also the creation of texts with extremist content. If earlier investigative practice encountered only the figure of the Distributor, then from now on, a completely new figure, the Author, should enter the field of professional vision of operatives. Apparently, this innovation will cause certain difficulties in investigative and judicial practice: distribution is a concrete, physical act, while the creation of a text is a creative process that is not fixed by the usual methods of forensic science. The appearance of a new person involved in the event of extremist activity logically motivates interest in the categories and methods of forensic authorship and, more broadly, humanitarian expertise.

1. Tasks and methods of forensic-author's expertise Depending on the tasks set, the author's research can have an identification and non-identification (classification) character.

Identification forensic expert examination aims to establish the authorship of the text. In this case, a typical task for the expert commission is the question of whether the text has the only author - or the text was created by a group of people, whether the authorship of the texts submitted for research is identical, whether a particular person can be the author of the submitted text, etc.

Diagnostic forensic expertise is designed to model the probabilistic appearance of the author of a particular text: to establish (diagnose) his gender, age, level of education, nationality, origin, residence, social and cultural affiliation, i.e. the expert must evaluate the hypothetical author of the text according to all available classification, anthropometric parameters. In practice, identification and diagnostic installations are often combined as part of a single comprehensive study.

This happens in those cases when, on the one hand, a test array with known authorship is offered to the expert commission for analysis, on the other hand, an anonymous text; experts are asked to answer whether the authorship of these texts is identical. Another option is also possible: the expert commission is introduced to the identity of the alleged author, then the

problematic text itself is offered for analysis; specialists in this case must answer the question of whether this person could write the presented text.

In the considered cases, the specialists-authorologists are actually given the task of an identification nature - to establish the author. But to solve this specific problem, it is first necessary to conduct a deep diagnostic study, designed to clarify the gender, age, cultural, and social affiliation of the author of the text of interest to the investigation; then "impose" these characteristics on the known personality of the suspect or the hypothetical personality of the author of the texts proposed for comparison. If these diagnostic characteristics match, then the probability of positive (identical) authorship increases. Thus, the described complex method involves a two-part study: the first phase is diagnostic, the second is comparative, while the conclusion of the examination is identification (actually the answer to the question of authorship).

In a number of cases, the author's identification expertise does without a preparatory classification phase. This technique is relevant in the case when an expert linguist obviously does not have sufficient knowledge in the field of psycho-, sociolinguistics and does not take responsibility for determining the gender, social and cultural identity of the author. Such an expert is based solely on linguistic data: the specialist compares the style (lexical and syntactic) features of the texts submitted for research and draws conclusions about their identical / non-identical authorship.

A purely identification study also takes place in cases where the author's expertise is based on a statistical method: in the compared texts, the frequency of using units of a certain type (prepositions, punctuation marks, syntactic constructions, etc.) is established, based on these data, conclusions are drawn about the speech manner the author of each of the texts, as well as the degree of closeness of these speech manners. Methodological variations in forensic expertise are due not only and not so much to the knowledge and skills of specialists. To a greater extent, the choice of the dominant method is influenced by the nature of the investigation itself.

It is one thing if you want to establish the authorship of a slanderous note; it is quite another when the task of the investigation is to restore the name of the true author on the cover of the novel. In the first case, the volume of the text is very small, and the creator is a person with poor writing skills. With such initial data, an expert is unlikely to base his research on a statistical method. In the second - a large text, and the author will definitely show an individual professional style of writing. Here the statistical method will be quite appropriate.

2. Judicial author's research in the investigation of manifestations of extremism In the context of the investigation of acts of extremism, the author's research becomes specific. It lies in the fact that a number of categories that are relevant for any author's expertise are completely irrelevant for research on extremist material. The reverse is also true: the investigation into extremism emphasizes optional, non-demonstrative (in most cases) aspects in the author's study, endowing them with special significance. Such features are often dictated by the properties of extremism as a cultural phenomenon.

2.1. Problematic application of the statistical method. The first limitation that extremist material imposes on the author's research is the impossibility of using the statistical method as the main one. The essence of the statistical method has already been briefly described above. Now let's take a closer look at the procedure for such a study. Statistical research is usually performed by machine. Here, computer technology is at the service of an expert. The studied text is "calculated" according to the selected parameters (the number of commas, colons, syntactic constructions of a certain type, letter combinations and other units).

Statistical indicators are summarized and stored by the machine. Then (and this is the key point) the computer program compares the resulting statistical pattern with the samples of author's manners already available in the program catalog. The result is the answer of the machine about the degree of conformity of the style of the author of the studied text with the style of any author (authors) from among those included in the catalog. While an extremist author is unlikely to be included in such a catalog in advance. The statistical method is more suitable for establishing the authorship of works of art - and then if there is a suspicion that they were written by one of the famous writers already researched and cataloged.

Extremist literature, and extremism in general, is a protest and marginal phenomenon in its essence. This literature is anonymous, small circulation, piece. An extremist work is aimed at popularizing a generally significant idea, while a literary text promotes the position of a particular author to the masses. The artistic text is rigidly tied to the image of the author, his other works and statements, i.e. literary and artistic text is included in the continuum of individual author's creativity and only in this context acquires semantic fullness.

Apparently, no one will ever be able to trace the work of an extremist author: his works are aimed at creating a social explosion, and in a certain sense they themselves are an explosion, a flash, a bright, but one-time phenomenon. Therefore, the fixation and cataloging of the work of such an author seems unlikely⁵ There is one way out of this situation: it is possible to "calculate" and catalog the author's styles specifically for a specific author's expertise. In this case, the investigating officer provides a work of unknown authorship, as well as texts with declared and confirmed authorship.

On the basis of the latter, conclusions about the author's style are made by the "calculation" method, then the authorship of the anonymous text is positive or negative. However, the problem lies in the fact that in most cases, the object of author's research in the framework of the investigation on extremism is small cycles of short works, or even single leaflet texts.

While the statistical pattern of the individual author's style can be identified with a satisfactory error only on extensive linguistic material (for example, a cycle of novels). The statistical method can be used in the author's study of extremist materials - but as an additional method, since statistical data obtained on a small material have a large mathematical error.

2.2. Irrelevance of categories of gender and dialect. The most important phase of any author's research is the procedure for establishing the gender of the author. To do this, it turns out to what extent the text implements the male or female speech manner. The scientific foundation of such research is the actively developing humanitarian science of genderology - the science of

"male" and "female", in all aspects of this problem. In linguistic genderology, no one disputes the postulate that male and female speech have their own characteristics.

Thus, the following indicative characteristics were identified for male speech: more frequent use of introductory words (with the meaning of a statement), abstract nouns, poor vocabulary when conveying emotions. Women's speech is characterized by a preference for modal constructions with the meaning of uncertainty, a tendency to use bookish vocabulary, prestige forms, speech clichés and clichés, as well as connotatively neutral words and euphemisms [Gaumont, 1990, p. 96–97]. “The male text is shorter than the female text, it contains more errors, fewer negative particles and prefixes, fewer terms of semantic non-exclusivity, a greater variety of vocabulary and fewer speech clichés.

A qualitative analysis of men's texts showed that they contain much fewer descriptions and references to their emotions, especially those that are not consistent with the image of a “real man”. The women's text, on the contrary, is more reminiscent of speech in a state of emotional stress: it will contain many negative particles, terms of semantic inexclusivity, speech clichés and clichés that are often used incorrectly, in addition, women's texts often contain references to their own various emotions” [Goroshko , 2003, p. 134; Oshchepkov, 2003, p. 102].

As you can see, the gender features of speech are well studied and generalized. The application of the described signs of male and female speech to a specific text makes it possible to speak with a high degree of probability about the gender of the author, which in some cases significantly advances the investigation. However, with regard to extremist materials, gender research is losing its fundamental significance. This is due to the rigid gender specificity of extremism as a cultural phenomenon: this area is characterized by a pronounced masculinity that does not allow feminine manifestations in thinking, behavior or speech. That is, the author of an extremist work will always be a man, it would be more correct to say “male consciousness”.

In reality, it is quite possible that an extremist text is written by a woman, but the consciousness of this woman will be significantly changed - under the influence of a cultural environment that cultivates masculinity. Such a woman will consciously modify her speech, ridding her of feminine features. The goal of the writer in this case is not to disguise authorship, but to be accepted among “her own”, to be adequate to the environment. Here it is worth noting that forensic autonomy has methods for identifying cases of imitation of someone else's speech manner. For example, a linguist can determine that a text is written by a man emitting female speech, and vice versa.

In the process of imitation, as a rule, only signs of the emitter that are obvious to the emitter are transmitted, while the deep specificity of speech generation, manifested in subtle elements, betrays the true author [Gaumont, 1990, p. 96–97]. However, even this tactic is ineffective in cases of extremism. The text of an extremist woman will implement not only obvious male speech features (slang, prison-like, and military vocabulary, simple syntax, “male” themes), but also the finest nuances of masculine discourse (abstract vocabulary, “liberty” of style, directness of nominations) . As already mentioned, under the influence of the environment, the very consciousness of an extremist woman, her style of thinking and speech production is

modified. Therefore, it is practically impossible to determine the sexual “forgery” by the methods of auto-science in this case.

Thus, the work to establish the gender of the author of an extremist text is redundant: its result is absolutely predictable.

Another productive stage of typical author's research is the analysis of the dialect features of the text. The meaning of this work is to establish the place of birth and upbringing, as well as the place of residence of the author of the text. A dialect is a regional variant of a language. Depending on the area of existence, the Russian language acquires features in sound, lexical composition, and grammatical form change (special case endings, ways of forming tense forms of the verb). Less often, regional features are manifested in syntax (methods of constructing a sentence).

References:

1. Gomon T.V. Research of documents with a deformed internal structure: dis. ... cand. legal Sciences. - M., 1990.
2. Goroshko E.I. Forensic and author's classification expertise: the problem of establishing the gender of the document's author // Theory and practice of ship's expertise and criminalistics: zb. sci.-pract. materials of conf. - Kharkiv: Law, 2003. - VIP. 3.
3. Oshchepkov E.S. Identification of the gender of the author according to the written text (lexical and grammatical aspect): dis. ... cand. philol. Sciences. - M., 2003. - 140 p.